

Abstract: the prognosis of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) disease has changed due to the advent of combination antiretroviral therapy (cART). HIV infection is still associated to different oral manifestations, as well as periodontal diseases. The article published in English from 2000 to 2021 in PUBMED/MEDLINE and Google Scholar databases were search electronically, using HIV infection and periodontal diseases as search terms. Eight papers were selected after application of all inclusion and exclusion criteria and reviewed critically. The results displayed that there was a significantly high prevalence of periodontitis in the ART-naïve compared to the ART experienced group. In the cART era, as in the pre cART era correlations between CD4 and/or HIV viral load with periodontal attachment loss or pocket depth have been inconclusive. some studies have demonstrated no differences in microbiota between HIV infected cART patients and non HIV infected patients while other studies have shown marked differences. In HIV infected patients, a full range of viruses have been isolated from both necrotic periodontitis as well as chronic periodontitis. In the pre-cART era, the invasion of candida into the periodontal soft tissues appeared to be directly connected with the occurrence of atypical periodontal lesions. patients with reduced bone mineralization, particularly in the more severe forms of osteoporosis are more prone to periodontal breakdown.

Introduction: Over the past 40 years the prognosis of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) disease has changed dramatically from a disease with a high mortality rate phase to a manageable chronic condition. This change is due to the advent of combination antiretroviral therapy (cART). ART-naïve patients are those who have never been on antiretroviral treatment with respect to their HIV status, and ART-experienced patients are those who are on antiretroviral treatment. HIV infection is still associated to different oral manifestations, as well as periodontal diseases. The first cases of the unusual periodontal diseases and conditions associated with HIV, including linear gingival erythema, necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis and necrotizing ulcerative periodontitis were published 3 decades ago.

Periodontal Diseases Associated with HIV Infection: A Review

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Methods and Materials: The article published in English from 2000 to 2021 in PUBMED/MEDLINE and Google Scholar databases were search electronically, using HIV infection and periodontal diseases as search terms. Eight papers were selected after application of all inclusion and exclusion criteria and reviewed critically.

Results: The results displayed that there was a significantly high prevalence of periodontitis in the ART-naïve (53.2%) compared to the ART experienced group (37.3%), with a two fold increased risk of the ART-naïve population presenting with periodontitis. In the ART-experienced population, there was no significant relationship between the prevalence of periodontitis and the various ART regimens ($p=0.10$).

Discussion: Before the advent of cART, atypical lesions involving the periodontal tissues were observed including linear gingival erythema (Figure 1) and a range of necrotizing periodontal diseases either restricted to the gingiva per se (e.g. necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis), or extending further into the periodontium to involve the soft tissue attachment and alveolar bone (e.g. necrotizing ulcerative periodontitis (Figure 1)). Similar lesions involving the adjacent hard and soft tissues of the mandible, maxilla, hard palate and buccal vestibule (necrotizing stomatitis) were also described. With the advent of cART a marked decline in the frequency of destructive periodontal disease in HIV patients has been reported. In the cART era, as in the pre cART era correlations between CD4 and/or HIV viral load with periodontal attachment loss or pocket depth have been inconclusive with some studies reporting no major differences in other periodontal parameters between HIV infected and non-infected patients or in tooth loss patterns particularly for patients with CD4 counts ≥ 500 . By contrast patients under cART who may have either developed a resistance to cART or lack of compliance to therapy and who experienced a 10-fold increase in viral load did show a marginal increase in tooth loss. some studies have demonstrated no differences in microbiota between HIV infected cART patients and non HIV infected patients while other studies have shown marked differences. For example, in patients on cART, Enterococcus faecalis and Fusobacterium nucleatum were observed in higher numbers inversely related to lower CD4 counts. However, in the cART era there continue to be reports of atypical/opportunistic microbial species isolated from the periodontal pockets of HIV patients. For example, some recent reports have demonstrated that in HIV patients, opportunistic pathogens such as Helicobacter pylori, E. faecalis and Pseudomonas aeruginosa are still detected in higher frequency in the subgingival biofilm. In HIV infected patients, a full range of viruses including cytomegalovirus, herpes zoster and human papilloma virus have been isolated from both necrotic periodontitis as well as chronic periodontitis. In particular for chronic periodontitis, viruses in the herpesvirus family which include cytomegalovirus, Epstein-Barr virus, and herpes simplex virus and have also been detected in periodontal pockets of HIV infected patients, and are found in higher numbers when compared to HIV non-infected patients. In the pre-cART era, the invasion of candida into the periodontal soft tissues appeared to be directly connected with the occurrence of atypical periodontal lesions including linear gingival erythema, and necrotizing ulcerative gingivitis and necrotizing ulcerative periodontitis. In addition, this candida induced inflammatory response may promote loss of clinical attachment and resorption of alveolar bone in chronic or aggressive periodontal diseases in the HIV positive patient. Osteoporosis has been reported to be more prevalent in HIV patients including those under cART. In a population of HIV infected younger men, the levels of bone mineralization were reported to be lower than their HIV uninfected counterparts. It is now well established that patients with reduced bone mineralization, particularly in the more severe forms of osteoporosis are more prone to periodontal breakdown.

Figure 1